

Circular and Bio-Based Solutions for the **U**ltimate **P**revention of **P**lastics in **R**ivers Integrated with **E**limination **A**nd **M**onitoring Technologies

Deliverable D6.1 DCCES Strategy

Deliverable information

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Disclaimer

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Executive Summary

UPSTREAM project aims to improve the cleanliness and water quality of the rivers by deploying and demonstrating into 5 demo sites a suite of 15 advanced solutions to deal with pollution in terms of litter, plastic and microplastic in European rivers. This challenge is afforded by a consortium (22 partners from 11 countries), from top European Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs), specialized Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SME) technology providers, a large company and completed by promoting a strong engagement of citizens and stakeholders. This complex scenario requires a well oriented organization for implementation and effective monitoring based on efficient and clear management tools and assignments.

Deliverable D6.1: “Dissemination, Communication, Community Engagement (DCCE) Strategy”, is implemented under WP6: “Knowledge co-creation, community engagement & dissemination”, and in particular under Task 6.1: “Dissemination, Communication, Community Engagement Strategy”. This report contains the development of the UPSTREAM’s visual identity, including logo, typography, colours, external communication materials (leaflet, poster, roll-up, flag, and infographic), templates (meeting minutes, participant list, agenda, deliverable, consent form, and presentation) as well as UPSTREAM’s general project presentation, social media account, webmail, website development launch, and dissemination activities.

Deliverable Keywords: UPSTREAM, communication, key stakeholders, community engagement strategy branding, identity release.

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Table of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
A1 format	Paper size 594×841 mm
A3 format	Paper size 297×420 mm
CMYK	Cyan, Magenta, Yellow, Black
DCCES	Dissemination, Communication, Community Engagement Strategy
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ID	Identity
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
L	Litter
MP	Microplastic
P	Plastic
RGB	Red, Green, Blue
RTO	Research and Technology Organisations
SC	Steering Committee
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
UKRI	UK Research and Innovation
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
WWTPs	Wastewater treatment plants

1. Introduction

1.1. Project overview

UPSTREAM is a European Union Horizon Europe programme with Grant Agreement number 101112877, that will run for 48 months with starting date 1st of September 2023. The current problem of litter (L), plastics (P), and microplastics (MP) in the European river systems needs to be addressed. Isolated actions are not enough, and consequently, actions should be taken along the water supply chain: before wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs), after WWTPs and in the rivers themselves.

The overall objective of UPSTREAM is to (i) address pollution at every point in the path of L, P, and MP, (ii) coupling the technical demonstrations with analysis of circular (bio-based) value chains, environmental and economic sustainability assessments, and focused efforts on knowledge co-creation and replication will accelerate the reduction of pollution in European rivers and (iii) engage stakeholders at all levels – industry, government, and citizens.

To do that, the UPSTREAM project is going to deploy and demonstrate into 5 demo sites a suite of 15 advanced solutions that address the serious issues of pollution from L, P, MP in European rivers along 5 pillars – monitoring, prevention, elimination at wastewater treatment plants, elimination from rivers, and valorisation of collected plastics. Besides, replication across Europe will be enhanced by means of a cascade funding initiative to join early adopters beyond the partnership to quickly scale up the solutions, contribute to the Mission objectives, and expand the water system knowledge base throughout Europe.

UPSTREAM represents a pan-European consortium with 5 demo sites across Europe, including 4 WWTPs (UK, ES, DE, IT), plus a testing area on the Danube in Serbia. The consortium (22 partners from 11 countries) is strengthened by top European Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs), specialized Small and medium-sized enterprises (SME) technology providers, a large company world leader in sustainable bioplastics development, Novamont, and completed by partners dedicated to creating a digital knowledge sharing platform and engaging with citizens and stakeholders.

1.2. Project communication and dissemination

Project communication and dissemination are crucial aspects of the UPSTREAM project, especially in the context of raising people's awareness of plastic pollution. Effective communication ensures transparency about the project's goals, activities, and outcomes. It allows stakeholders, organisations, RTO's, industry, and the public, to understand what impact the project is expected to achieve.

Dissemination activities will be undertaken to promote and publicly disclose the project results to specific target audiences that may make use of the results and enable their uptake. Specific focus will be given to replicating the technologies across Europe, especially in regions not previously active in Mission Ocean projects. Several measures will be planned and undertaken to circulate knowledge and results to those who can best use them.

Communication activities will be undertaken to promote the project and results to a broad audience, including the general public and audiences outside the specialist fields of the project. Effort will be made to demonstrate how EU funding is tackling societal challenges with particular focus on generating support

for plastics elimination solutions. A key theme throughout the DE&C activities will be increased awareness of the need to prevent pollution in rivers through the engagement of citizens and other key stakeholders.

2. Key stakeholder groups

In relation to *Task 6.1, Dissemination, Communication, Community Engagement strategy*, ZINNAE provides to the consortium a game plan to identify and build the communities of key stakeholder groups. The focus is on the initially identified stakeholders, meaning individuals or organisations that are affected or affect UPSTREAM project and have an interest in it or its results.

The UPSTREAM project is an initiative focused on addressing plastic pollution in the rivers. The project's main objective is to develop innovative solutions to prevent plastic from entering the aquatic environment, with a particular focus on managing plastic waste in rivers and waterways. Some of the activities carried out under the UPSTREAM project include research on the sources and pathways of plastic entry into river systems, the development of technologies and strategies to prevent, monitor, eliminate and valorise plastic pollution, public awareness-raising, and stakeholder engagement.

UPSTREAM promotes a more sustainable circular economy. By identifying innovative solutions and fostering collaboration among diverse stakeholders, the project is expected to contribute to reducing the amount of plastic reaching the oceans and thus protect the aquatic environment and marine life. The stakeholders are: industry, scientists' community (research&development), national and European policy makers, environmental sustainability stakeholders, general public among others.

2.1. Water utilities

Companies or entities responsible for providing services related to drinking water supply and wastewater treatment. These organisations are responsible for managing the infrastructure necessary to ensure the supply of drinking water to communities, as well as to collect, treat and dispose of wastewater in a safe and efficient manner.

Their responsibilities include the operation and maintenance of drinking water and wastewater treatment plants, the distribution of drinking water through piped networks, the collection and disposal of wastewater and the management of flood control infrastructure and the protection of the aquatic environment, would therefore be our first priority for the communication strategy in UPSTREAM project.

2.2. Business community

2.2.1. Solution providers

We are interested in companies that are either water-smart solutions providers or/and looking for water solutions to eliminate litter, plastics and microplastics in rivers, wastewater treatment plants and water purification companies that participate actively in the removal of contaminants of emerging concern.

These companies are dedicated to treating wastewater to remove contaminants and return treated water to the environment or reuse it in applications such as agricultural irrigation or industrial use.

Water treatment technology and equipment companies that develop and manufacture equipment and technologies for water treatment, such as filtration systems, purification, desalination, water quality sensors and engineering firms that design and implement infrastructure and projects related to water, such as wastewater treatment plants, irrigation systems, water distribution networks, can be the final targets of project dissemination.

Also of special relevance are the entities dedicated to the monitoring and control of plastic, microplastics and litter pollution in rivers, as well as entities focused on the development of biodegradable materials to substitute conventional fossil-based plastics in: i) personal care and cosmetic products, textile fibres and; ii) plastic carriers for Moving Beds Biofilm Reactors (MBBR) used in WWTP.

To a lesser extent, they can also be relevant environmental consulting firms that provide consultancy and advisory services on water management issues, such as environmental impact assessment, water quality studies, design of water management policies and programs, among others.

2.2.2. End users

The targeted end-users of UPSTREAM's communication activities could include municipalities and local authorities responsible for the management and distribution of drinking water and for the treatment of wastewater in urban areas, and some industries that use water in their production processes and may require solutions for efficient and sustainable water resource management. Households and communities (final consumers) that use drinking water for domestic purposes may be interested in solutions to improve the quality of the water they consume.

Indirectly we are also interested in companies that want to valorise the collected plastics and offer a second use for them, and companies that are focused on raw materials valorisation in general terms.

2.2.3. Industrial ecosystems

We are interested in the industrial ecosystem especially linked to wastewater treatment, textile industry, cutlery, cosmetics and personal care products industry. UPSTREAM will connect companies from these ecosystems with solution providers and demo sites. Leading water treatment and textile industry actors are very present in the regional ecosystems where the UPSTREAM project is present.

The textile industry is a major source of microplastics due to the widespread use of synthetic fibres such as polyester, nylon, and acrylic in the manufacturing of clothing. During the washing of these garments, small plastic particles are released into the water, contributing to microplastic pollution in oceans and water bodies. On the other hand, cosmetics and personal care industry, such as exfoliants, creams, and lotions, contain microplastics in the form of microbeads or microspheres. These microplastics can be

released into the environment when they are rinsed down the drain, contributing to pollution in water bodies.

2.3. Research institutions, technological centres and universities

Research institutions, technological centres and universities will also be associated with the project at regional, national and European levels. UPSTREAM will establish cooperation with educational and research institutions to boost the development of the project and they will also benefit from the project through demo sites or pilot cases that UPSTREAM will implement as part of the actions in the project.

2.4. Policy makers

DG ENV; DG GROW; DG REGIO, DG RTD, Relevant national ministries; Regional government; municipalities.

Regional, national, and European policy and related strategies can be positively influenced by the results achieved within the project. They will be actively engaged with, to enhance project delivery, policy synergies and also the long-term project sustainability. UPSTREAM will seek to ensure the project is creating synergies with other regions.

European Union plays a crucial role in promoting environmental and sustainability policies across Europe. The European Commission is responsible for proposing legislation, implementing policies, and coordinating actions among member states in areas such as environmental protection, waste management, biodiversity conservation, and combating climate change.

National and regional governments play an important role in formulating and implementing environmental and sustainability policies at the local level. These governments can establish regulations, provide incentives and funding for environmental projects, and promote sustainable practices in sectors such as agriculture or industry.

2.5. Clusters in targeted sectors and cluster associations

Partners and clusters part of their networks related to water thematic and key targeted industrial sectors will be a key target of the project activities. Some of the following organisation, platforms, projects and networks may be contacted to help us deliver the best communication results: CIW, EuroBoostEX, BEM, WCF, CREA, SWA, CWP, LE2C, CLEAN, International Cleantech Network, ACLIMA, Vegepoly Valley, AEI TÈXTILS, ATEVAL, CITEVE, TECHTERA, OTIR2020-TFC - Next Technology Tecnotessile, TEXTGLOBAL, GALACTICA, EU-TEXTILE2030, Packaging Cluster, European Strategic Cluster Partnership for Advanced Smart Packaging, Beauty cluster, C4W, GCC.eu, the national cluster associations in the partner countries,

the European Cluster Alliance, and the European Cluster Collaboration Platform (ECCP). Clusters, thanks to their knowledge of their members, can help create these linkages but also provide the link to other cluster ecosystems.

Clusters associations will disseminate the information of the UPSTREAM project to gain valuable knowledge on water solutions to eliminate litter, plastics and microplastics in rivers, and improve the understanding of waste valorisation for sustainable resource management and environmental protection.

2.6. European, national, and regional organisations and networks supporting innovation

UPSTREAM project wishes to team up with other networks and partners to build a strong Alliance supporting the monitoring, prevention, elimination, and valorisation of litter, plastics and microplastics, like a complementary brick to the existing supported services at regional, national and EU scale.

Some of the following organisation, platforms, projects and networks may be contacted to help us deliver the best results: Water4all, Water Europe, Finnish Water Forum, Global Water Tech Hub Alliance, Pact For Skills, EEN, Cosmetics Europe, European Fashion Alliance, Plastics Europe, Circular Plastics Alliance, European Plastics Pact, CUSP, Digital Innovation Hubs and Regional development agencies.

The collaboration with European, national, regional organisations and networks specialised in water as well as litter, plastics and microplastics issues will enable UPSTREAM project to establish a strong alliance supporting the display of results on demo sites.

2.7. Environmental sustainability stakeholders

Environmental agencies and bodies dedicated to environmental protection and sustainability promotion are involved in promoting environmental sustainability at different levels. For example, the European Environment Agency (EEA) is an agency of the European Union whose task is to provide sound and independent information on the environment. It is the main source of information for those responsible for developing, adopting, implementing and evaluating environmental policies, as well as for citizens.

Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) in Europe dedicated to environmental protection and sustainability promotion are also important. These organizations play an important role in public awareness, advocacy for environmental policies, citizen participation, and implementation of conservation and sustainable development projects. Some possibilities are mentioned below:

- European Water Partnership (EWP): this Belgium-based organization brings together various stakeholders, including governments, businesses, NGOs, and research centres, to address water-related challenges in Europe and promote sustainable water management.
- European Water Association (EWA): EWA is a Germany-based organization that gathers professionals and experts in the water sector from across Europe. It works in areas such as water quality, water resources management, and water infrastructure.
- New Water Culture Foundation (FNCA): This Spain-based organization promotes an integrated and sustainable approach to water management in Europe, focusing on citizen participation, water governance, and protection of aquatic ecosystems.
- Plastics Europe: a professional association representing plastics manufacturers in Europe. Its core mission is to promote the responsible and sustainable use of plastics and to advocate policies and practices that drive innovation, efficiency, and safety in the plastics industry.
- EPRO: European Association of Plastics Recycling and Recovery Organisations is an international partnership of specialist organisations that are working to develop and deliver efficient solutions for the sustainable management of plastics resources, now and for the future.
- European Environmental Bureau (EEB): network of more than 140 environmental organisations across Europe. Their aim is to influence European Union (EU) environmental policies and to promote the protection of the environment and human health throughout Europe. They work on a variety of issues, such as air quality, water, renewable energy, waste management and biodiversity conservation, and work closely with European institutions, national governments, and other stakeholders to influence European environmental policies.
- Greenpeace: one of the world's most recognised environmental organisations dedicated to protecting the environment and promoting peace, focusing on issues such as climate change, biodiversity conservation, ocean protection and the elimination of toxic substances.
- World Wide Fund for Nature Europe (WWF Europe): international organisation dedicated to the conservation of nature and the protection of species around the world. WWF Europe works in partnership with governments, businesses, and local communities to address pressing environmental issues and promote sustainable practices across Europe.
- ECODES: works in the field of development cooperation, promotion of social justice, and environmental protection. ECODES develops projects and campaigns in collaboration with different social actors, public institutions, and businesses, with the aim of promoting sustainable development that respects human rights and protects the environment.
- Ellen MacArthur Foundation: Is a charity committed to creating a circular economy, which is designed to eliminate waste and pollution, circulate products and materials, and regenerate nature. It's network brings together industry leading corporations, emerging innovators, affiliate networks, government authorities, regions, cities and more.

2.8. General public

Reaching the general public is essential for raising awareness, fostering participation and support, promoting behavioural change, and contributing to the implementation of effective solutions against plastic pollution.

Public awareness about plastic pollution and its environmental impacts is crucial for generating significant changes in behaviours and policies, because the project can increase pressure on decision-makers to take concrete action. By reaching the general public, the UPSTREAM project can educate and inform people about the severity of the problem and the importance of addressing it. Involving the general public in identifying solutions and implementing actions is critical for the long-term success of the project. By fostering citizen participation, UPSTREAM can leverage local knowledge and community engagement to develop and implement effective measures against plastic pollution. Individual and community-level behaviour change is crucial for reducing plastic pollution. By reaching the general public, UPSTREAM can inspire and motivate people to adopt more sustainable practices in their daily lives, such as reducing single-use plastics, recycling correctly, and participating in community clean-ups.

The UPSTREAM project can promote the transition to a circular economy, where the consumption of virgin plastics is reduced and recycling and reuse are encouraged. By reaching the general public, the project can promote the adoption of more responsible consumption habits and support local initiatives that promote the circular economy.

3. UPSTREAM visual identity

3.1. UPSTREAM Brand guidelines

UPSTREAM Brand guidelines content main logo design, logo structure, typography structure, exclusion zone, logo colours variations, logo usage, app icon, logo colour, logo typography, project name typography, and text typography.

Brand Guidelines

Upstream

FOR WASTE-FREE EUROPEAN RIVERS

Circular and Bio-Based Solutions for the **Ultimate** Prevention of Plastics in **Rivers**
Integrated with **Elimination** And **Monitoring** Technologies

Call: HORIZON-MISS-2022-OCEAN-01-04
Prevent and eliminate litter, plastics and MP: Innovative solutions for
waste-free European Rivers

Branding Logo Book Guidelines

Co-funded by
the European Union

Volume 1

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**Main Logo
Primary Colors**

The main logo is the face of Logo Name the primary visual expression that we use to identity the project, meaning that we need to be careful to use it correctly and to do so consislyenly.

Upstream
FOR WASTE-FREE EUROPEAN RIVERS

Volume 1

Branding Logo Book Guidelines

01

**Main Logo
without Slogan**

Upstream

Volume 1

Branding Logo Book Guidelines

02

Exclusion Zone

Make sure that text or other design elements do not encroach on the logo. The marked space should always be given so logo can be free from any distraction.

Branding Logo Book Guidelines

Volume 1

07

Logo Colors Variations

“Brand Name” logo used on an application will often depend on the background and production method.

Branding Logo Book Guidelines

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Full Color

One Color

08

Logo Usage

Branding Logo Book Guidelines

DO NOT
resize or change the position of the logomark.

DO NOT
move any parts of the logo.

DO NOT
change the distance.

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App Icon

Branding Logo Book Guidelines

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10

Logo Color

Colors are as important to our brand as the logos themselves. Just as punctuation and volume set the tone for our verbal and written style, color sets the tone for our visual style.

Branding Logo Book Guidelines

Color Name #bbe3f2	R187 G227 B242 C24 M1 Y3 K0
Color Name #94c7e0	R148 G199 B224 C40 M9 Y6 K0
Color Name #49a8e2	R73 G168 B226 C64 M19 Y0 K0
Color Name #1d5760	R29 G87 B96 C88 M52 Y50 K27
Color Name #58595b	R88 G89 B91 C64 M56 Y53 K28

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Logo Typography

The typeface we use help us to convey personality of our brand. Consistent use of typography will build an immediately recognizable identity for over time.

Branding Logo Book Guidelines

Comfortaa Bold Comfortaa Light

Acumin Variable Concept

Comfortaa Bold

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii
Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oom Pp Qq Rr
Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

1234567890!@#\$\$%^&*()

Comfortaa Light

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii
Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oom Pp Qq Rr
Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

1234567890!@#\$\$%^&*()

Acumin Variable Concept

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii
Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oom Pp Qq Rr
Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

1234567890!@#\$\$%^&*()

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Figure 1: Brand guidelines.

3.1.1. UPSTREAM Logo

The logo name was selected to fit the nature of the project. The UPSTREAM name was composed by sentence: “Circular and Bio-Based Solutions for the **U**ltimate **P**revention of **P**lastics in **R**ivers Integrated with **E**limination **A**nd **M**onitoring Technologies”.

Figure 2: UPSTREAM Logo.

Figure 3: UPSTREAM Logo without slogan.

Figure 4: UPSTREAM Logo (grayscale).

Figure 5: UPSTREAM Logo (white).

The UPSTREAM logo is based on two main colours: blue and green in different intensities. The blue-green colour scheme is playful and refers to the project identity's connection to nature.

Figure 6: UPSTREAM Logo colours.

Typography is a powerful tool for establishing and reinforcing project brand identity. Consistency in typography across various brand touchpoints such as logos, websites, advertisements, and promotional materials will help create a cohesive and recognizable project brand identity.

Figure 7: UPSTREAM Logo fonts.

Figure 8: Project title fonts.

3.1.2. UPSTREAM Typography

Typography refers to use of fonts and text styles in the design and presentation of a project. It plays a crucial role in conveying information, establishing visual hierarchy, and creating a cohesive and engaging visual identity.

The Comfortaa Font Family is used for titles (promotional materials such as poster, roll-up, etc), the Calibri Font Family is used for regular text (Meeting Minutes, Deliverables, etc), the Acumin Pro Font Family is

used text in promotional materials such as poster, roll-up, etc, and Brushmosh font is used for project slogan.

Comfortaa Font Family:	
Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oom Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz	Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oom Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz
1234567890!@#\$%^&*()	1234567890!@#\$%^&*()
Calibri Font Family:	
Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oom Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz	Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oom Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz
1234567890!@#\$%^&*()	1234567890!@#\$%^&*()
Acumin Pro Font Family:	
Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oom Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz	Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oom Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz
1234567890!@#\$%^&*()	1234567890!@#\$%^&*()
Brushmost Font:	
Brushmosh Regular	
Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oom Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz	
1234567890!@#\$%^&*()	FOR WASTE-FREE EUROPEAN RIVERS

Figure 9: UPSTREAM fonts.

FOR WASTE-FREE EUROPEAN RIVERS

Figure 10: Project slogan.

3.2. External communication materials

3.2.1. UPSTREAM Leaflet

The UPSTREAM leaflet is a communication material containing information on the identity of the project, its scope and the planned contribution to raising awareness of the need to prevent pollution in rivers through the engagement of citizens and other key stakeholders.

The leaflet is presented as a single fold format where some general information about the project, the partnership and the coordination are included, while also the concept, objectives and expected outcomes. The leaflet is available in a digital form to be forwarded via e-mail and in printed versions for conferences and live events.

P.1

P.2

P.3

P.4

Figure 11: UPSTREAM Leaflet.

3.2.2. UPSTREAM Poster

The UPSTREAM poster will be used to raise awareness of the need to prevent river pollution through the engagement of citizens and other key stakeholders.

The poster is designed in an attractive format and contains images, an infographic and a description of the project's objectives. The poster is available in digital and in printed version in A1 and A3 formats. It will be extensively used by UPSTREAM partners whenever they present at conferences, publish in journals and magazines, establish contacts with media, attend exhibitions, organise workshops, etc.

Figure 12: UPSTREAM Poster.

3.2.3. UPSTREAM Roll-up

The UPSTREAM roll-up will be used to raise awareness of the need to prevent river pollution through the engagement of citizens and other key stakeholders.

The roll-up is designed in an attractive format and contains images, an infographic and a description of the project's objectives. The format of roll-up is 100×200 cm. It will be extensively used by UPSTREAM partners whenever they present at conferences, publish in journals and magazines, establish contacts with media, attend exhibitions, organise workshops, etc.

Figure 13: UPSTREAM Roll-up.

3.2.4. UPSTREAM Flag

The promotional flag will be used as a high-visibility promotional tool at attendance events, conferences, workshops, demo sites, ... The flag is available in dimension 100×200 cm.

Figure 14: UPSTREAM Flag.

3.2.5. UPSTREAM Infographic

The following Figure 15 presents the infographics related to the overall project concept.

Figure 15: UPSTREAM Infographic.

3.3. Templates

In this section the templates for the Meeting minutes, Participant list, Agenda, Deliverable, Project’s presentation, and Consent, that the whole consortium will need and use, are presented. All are based on the project’s identity, as explained earlier, and making sure that a simple format is used for easy access.

3.3.1. Meeting Minutes template

The Meeting minutes template (Figure 16) will help the organisers of an event, or even participant partners to note all important information, including partners list, bullet point on discussed items, the actions and next steps, issues that need to be addressed, and the upcoming planned meeting.

Circular and Bio-Based Solutions for the Ultimate Prevention of Plastics in Rivers Integrated with Elimination And Monitoring Technologies

Meeting Minutes Title

Minutes written by | XXXX

Project profile

Programme	Horizon Europe
Call	HORIZON-MISS-2022-OCEAN-01-04
Number	101112877
Acronym	UPSTREAM
Name	Circular and Bio-Based Solutions for the Ultimate Prevention of Plastics in Rivers Integrated with Elimination And Monitoring Technologies
Start Date	1 September 2023
Duration	48 months
Type of action	HORIZON Innovation Actions
Granting authority	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
Project Coordinator	Fundacion AITIP

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Project partners

Organisation name	Short name	Country
iNeuvo Ltd	INEUVO	UK
Fundacion AITIP	AIT	ES
Acondicionamiento Tarrasense Asociacion – Leitlat	LEI	ES
Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek N.V.	VITO	BE
Kemijski Institut – National Institute of Chemistry	NIC	SI
NOVA ID FCT - Associacao Para a Inovacao e Desenvolvimento da FCT	NOVAID	PT
University of Novi Sad Faculty of Sciences	UNFS	RS
Panepistimio Aigaiou – University of Aegean	UoA	EL
The University of Birmingham	UoB	UK
UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology	CEH	UK
Wasser 3.0 GmbH	W30	DE
Van Remmen UV Techniek B.V.	VRE	NL
Nuevas Tecnologias Para el Desarrollo de Packaging y Productos Agroalimentarios Con Componente Plastica SL	TECHNO	ES
Eden Microfluidic Technologies	EDEN	FR
Le Quere – Boaxt	LEQ	FR
Think Ocean CIC	TOC	UK
Daphne Water Solutions Limited	DWS	UK
Novamont SPA	NVMT	IT
Severn Trent Water Limited	SVT	UK
Asociacion Cluster Para el Uso Eficiente Del Agua – Zinnac	ZIN	ES
EcoCiudad Zaragoza S.A.	ECO	ES
CAP Holding SPA	CAP	IT

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Title

WP1: Screening, mapping and monitoring systems

Update: text

Next Actions: text

WP2: Optimization of innovative enabling technologies

Update: text

Next Actions: text

WP3: Large scale demonstration

Update: text

Next Actions: text

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Title

WP4: Principles for circular (bio-based) design and assessment of impacts

Update: text

Next Actions: text

WP5: Cost-effective solutions, replication & sustainable exploitation management

Update: text

Next Actions: text

WP6: Knowledge co-creation, community engagement & dissemination

Update: text

Next Actions: text

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<p>Title </p> <p>Other Matters:</p> <p>Next Meeting</p> <p>Tentative Date: text here</p> <p>Location: text here</p>	
6 of 6 <small>Co-Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.</small>	

Figure 16: Meeting minutes template.

3.3.2. Participant list template

A template for the participants list can be found below, that will be used to gather data about the participants name and entity in every kind of event and meeting (Figure 17).

3.3.4. Deliverable template

Figure 19 shows the Deliverable Template that will be used throughout the 48 Months project with the details of the deliverable, project profile, document history, table styles, contents, and guidelines on how to use all the headings and text styles.

Circular and Bio-Based Solutions for the Ultimate Prevention of Plastics in Rivers Integrated with Elimination And Monitoring Technologies

Deliverable D.X.X
Title

Deliverable information

Responsible partner:	
Work package No and Title:	
Contributing partner(s):	
Dissemination level:	
Type:	
Due Date:	
Submission date:	
Version:	It refers to the version submitted to EC. Previous the first delivery (v1), refer it as v0.1, v0.2...

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 UK Research and Innovation

 EU MISSIONS
RESTORE OUR OCEAN & WATERS

DXX – Title

Project profile

Programme:	Horizon Europe
Call:	HORIZON-MISS-2022-OCEAN-01-04
Number:	101112877
Acronym:	UPSTREAM
Name:	Circular and Bio-Based Solutions for the Ultimate Prevention of Plastics in Rivers Integrated with Elimination And Monitoring Technologies
Start Date:	1 September 2023
Duration:	48 months
Type of action:	HORIZON Innovation Actions
Granting authority:	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
Project Coordinator:	Fundacion AITIIP

Document history

Version	Dates	Entity	Remarks

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 UK Research and Innovation

 EU MISSIONS
RESTORE OUR OCEAN & WATERS

2 of 10

<p style="text-align: right;">DXX – Title </p> <p style="font-size: x-small;">Co-Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.</p>	
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<p style="text-align: right;">DXX – Title </p> <p style="font-size: x-small;">Co-Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.</p>																																					
Deliverable information.....	1																																				
Project profile	2																																				
Document history	2																																				
Disclaimer	3																																				
Executive Summary	4																																				
Table of Contents.....	5																																				
List of Figures	6																																				
List of Tables	7																																				
Table of Abbreviations.....	8																																				
1. Introduction (style used: Heading 1).....	8																																				
1.1. Subtitle (style used: Heading 2).....	8																																				
2. Title (style used: Heading 1).....	8																																				
2.1. Subtitle (style used: Heading 2).....	8																																				
2.1.1. Subtitle (style used: Heading 3).....	8																																				
3. Title (style used: Heading 1).....	9																																				
4. Conclusions (style used: Heading 1).....	9																																				
5. References.....	10																																				
6. Annexes (style used: Heading 1).....	10																																				

DXX – Title

List of Tables

Table 1

Table of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition

1. Introduction (style used: Heading 1)

1.1. Subtitle (style used: Heading 2)

Text text text (style used: Body)

- Text (style used: bullet Body)

2. Title (style used: Heading 1)

2.1. Subtitle (style used: Heading 2)

Text text text (style used: Body)

2.1.1. Subtitle (style used: Heading 3)

Text text text (style used: Body)

2.1.1.1. Subtitle

Subtitle (style used: Heading 5)

Text text text (style used: Body)

In case you wish to include references use footnotes¹

¹ Include reference here

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DXX – Title

Upstream
 FOR WASTE-FREE EUROPEAN RIVERS
 Figure 1: Logo

Table 1: Insert title of table

3. Title (style used: Heading 1)

Table 2: Insert title of table

4. Conclusions (style used: Heading 1)

Expected Content:

- Summary of the main outputs and conclusions derived from the work reported in the framework of this deliverable
- How it has contributed to (i) the overall project goals and expected impacts and (ii) to Missions and EC goals

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DXX – Title

- Where applicable, highlight potential business benefits or future improvements considering best practices or roadmap forward.

5. References

There is not a specific style but please, be consistent with the style along the document. As example:

Journal publication:
[Number in the document] Authors (year). Title, Journal, vol, page-page. DOI.

URL:
[Number in the document] Author, (Year). Title. URL or page, last access date

Book:
[Number in the document] Author (2011). Chapter title in Book Title (ed). Place. Publisher.

6. Annexes (style used: Heading 1)

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Figure 19: Deliverable template

TASKS & SUBTASKS
(MX-MX)

FOR WASTE-FREE EUROPEAN RIVERS

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9

WORK DONE

Text

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REACHED RESULTS

Text

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WPX CONCLUSIONS

FOR WASTE-FREE EUROPEAN RIVERS

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WPX CONCLUSIONS

Text

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WPX CONCLUSIONS

Text

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WPX RISKS & ISSUES

FOR WASTE-FREE EUROPEAN RIVERS

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WPX RISKS & ISSUES

Text

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16

Figure 21: Presentation slides template.

3.3.7. UPSTREAM project presentation

UPSTREAM project presentation provides a concise overview of the project's purpose, objectives, impact, and expected outcomes. Figure 22 shows the general presentation of the project used when participating in events, conferences, meetings, etc.

Circular and Bio-Based Solutions for the Ultimate Prevention of Plastics in Rivers Integrated with Elimination And Monitoring Technologies

Co-funded by the European Union | UK Research and Innovation | MISSION 4

Ambitions

- improve the **cleanliness** and **water quality** of the **7 European rivers** that flow through several major European capitals and flow into 5 sea basins (Celtic, Mediterranean, Black and North Seas);
- the UPSTREAM project is based on the widespread deployment and demonstration of a suite of 15 advanced solutions that address the serious issues of pollution from litter (L), plastics (P), and microplastics (MP) in European rivers.

7 European rivers:

Severn Trent Ebro Ticino Olona Queich Danube

Co-funded by the European Union | UK Research and Innovation | MISSION 4

Project details

Call: HORIZON-MISS-2022-OCEAN-01-04 | Project Number: 101112877

Start date: 1 September 2023 | End date: 31 August 2027 | Duration: 4 years

EU contribution: € 7 024 032,90 | UK contribution: € 2 959 042,00

Co-funded by the European Union | UK Research and Innovation | MISSION 4

Consortium

22 partners | 11 countries
10 research institutes | 10 industrial partners | 2 associations

Project coordinator: Aitiip Technology Centre (Spain)

Co-funded by the European Union | UK Research and Innovation | MISSION 4

Objectives

The problem of litter (L), plastics (P), and microplastics (MP) in the European river systems needs to be addressed at several points in the water supply systems:

- before wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs)
- after wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs)
- in the rivers themselves

The overall objective of UPSTREAM is thus to address pollution at every point in the path of L, P, and MP, from creation until ending up in the seas, while engaging stakeholders at all levels – industry, government, and citizens.

Co-funded by the European Union | UK Research and Innovation | MISSION 4

5 Pillars:

- MONITORING** of L, P, and MP at 5 different WWTPs and river sites
- PREVENTION** innovative biobased, biodegradable materials
- ELIMINATION** from waste-treatment plants, collect 98% by mass of MP from the sludge
- ELIMINATION** remove 65 tonnes of L and P from Danube river and connected waterways
- VOLARISATION** of collected P and MP for different types of material use

Co-funded by the European Union | UK Research and Innovation | MISSION 4

Concept:

PREVENTION through biobased and biodegradable plastics 2 APPROACHES

- Personal care products
- Textile & clothing
- Rubber tyres
- Plastics pellets
- Microplastics

ELIMINATION from WWTP effluents 5 TECHNOLOGIES

ELIMINATION from WWTP sludge 1 TECHNOLOGY

MONITORING of litter, plastics, and microplastics 3 TECHNOLOGIES

ELIMINATION from rivers 2 TECHNOLOGIES

Microplastics entering water bodies from effluent water

Wastewater treatment plant

Sewage sludge spread on agricultural land

Volatilisation of collected plastics 2 TECHNOLOGIES

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5 Demonstration sites

- WWTP | United Kingdom (Severn and Trent rivers)
- WWTP | Spain (Ebro river)
- WWTP | Italy (Ticino and Olona rivers)
- WWTP | Germany (Queich river)
- Testing area on river | Serbia (Danube river)

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Figure 22: UPSTREAM project presentation.

4. UPSTREAM Social media

Engaging various stakeholders in EU project communication is essential for successful project implementation. Social media platforms have billions of active users worldwide, providing a vast audience for communication. This makes it an effective tool for reaching out to a large number of people quickly and efficiently.

Social media allows individuals and organizations to build their brand identity, establish credibility, and increase visibility. Consistent and engaging communication on social media can help attract followers, supporters, customers, and stakeholders. Overall, they play a crucial role in modern communication by facilitating widespread, instantaneous, and interactive communication, enabling targeted messaging, amplifying content, building brands, and providing valuable data and insights.

Hashtags

A hashtag is a word or phrase preceded by the "#" symbol, used on social media platforms to categorize content and make it discoverable by other users interested in that topic. Hashtags allow users to organize and search for content related to specific themes, events, or discussions. For the effective communication, reach, searching efficiency and branding of SM's campaigns, hashtags need to be used (and especially for LinkedIn, Facebook and X).

The UPSTREAM lead hashtag is **#ForWasteFreeEuropeanRivers**.

Other important hashtags are: #Upstream, #CleanRivers, #PlasticFreeRivers, #PreventPollution, #Environment, #EUmissions, #HorizonProject, #HorizonEurope

4.1. UPSTREAM LinkedIn account

LinkedIn, the professional networking platform, has become an indispensable tool for professionals across worldwide. With over 930 M users, LinkedIn is the fastest growing professional networking platform. Furthermore, professional networking provides access to a wide range of opportunities. Effective professional networking requires active participation through various channels such as attending conferences or industry-specific events, joining relevant professional organizations or online communities, participating in workshops or seminars, and utilizing social media platforms to connect with like-minded professionals.

LinkedIn will provide a range of opportunities for Upstream project to connect, collaborate, and promote its initiatives within the European and global community. By using LinkedIn effectively, stakeholders can enhance the impact, visibility, and success of the project. The LinkedIn account is an upgrade of the existing successful channel (Scientists against plastic edited by NIC) and has been renamed to Upstream Horizon. LinkedIn will be used to organise professional events, online workshops and seminars, and to inform the public and stakeholders about the progress of the Upstream project.

UPSTREAM LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/upstream-horizon-project/>

Figure 23: UPSTREAM LinkedIn account.

4.2. UPSTREAM Facebook account

Facebook is the largest social networking site, with over 3 billion people using it monthly, according to Statista. This means roughly 37 percent of the world's population are Facebook users. With Facebook, we will increase the recognition value of our projects, expand our online audience and spread awareness of Upstream project to the public. The Facebook account is an upgrade of the existing successful channel (Scientists against plastic edited by NIC) and has been renamed to Upstream Horizon.

UPSTREAM Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/upstream.horizon>

Figure 24: UPSTREAM Facebook account.

4.3. UPSTREAM X account

X (formerly Twitter) has become one of the most used social media with over 500 million users. Users can share and post short text messages, images, and videos known historically as "tweets".

UPSTREAM X: <https://twitter.com/UpstreamHorizon>

Figure 25: UPSTREAM X account.

4.4. UPSTREAM Instagram account

Instagram offers a powerful platform for Upstream project to visually communicate, engage with stakeholders, raise awareness, drive action, and ultimately, make a positive impact within the European community and beyond.

UPSTREAM Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/upstreamproject/>

Figure 26: UPSTREAM Instagram account.

5. UPSTREAM Webmail

Emails are the most extensive channel for communication for partners businesses, and it is important to facilitate the tracking of the communications inside of the project activities. Therefore, the word ‘UPSTREAM’ must be included at the beginning of the subject following with the description of the email. For example, if the email aims to provide information about the agenda for the next SC meeting, the structure will be:

Subject: UPSTREAM – 2nd SC meeting Agenda

Two e-mail accounts have been set up for the proper conduct of meetings, tasks, deadlines and communication in general:

- info@upstream-project.eu (the “info” e-mail is used for external communication within the general public; it is available on the Upstream website);
- consortium@upstream-project.eu (the “consortium” e-mail is used for internal communication within the consortium).

Figure 27: UPSTREAM Webmail.

6. UPSTREAM Website

Websites play a crucial role in today's digital age and serve as a central hub for information, communication and interaction. The UPSTREAM website serve as interactive communication platforms that enable two-way communication between the UPSTREAM project and its stakeholders.

The first version of UPSTREAM website has been launched in February 2024 and is accessible at this address: <https://upstream-project.eu/>

Current UPSTREAM Website has the following segments:

- Home (The project, Objectives, Impact, Work Packages, Deliverables)
- Pillars
- Demos sites
- Consortium
- Contact

The fully functional website will be periodically updated with all the latest information about UPSTREAM, news, and newsletters on the project activities, publications, and extract from public deliverables.

Figure 28: UPSTREAM Website.

To enable easy access to the project website, a QR code has been created that can be used in various documents and scanned with mobile devices.

Figure 29: UPSTREAM Website QR code

7. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

Dissemination activities will be undertaken to promote and publicly disclose the project results to specific target audiences that may make use of the results and enable their uptake. Specific focus will be given to replicating the technologies across Europe, especially in regions not previously active in Mission Ocean projects. Several measures will be planned and undertaken to circulate knowledge and results to those who can best use them.

Dissemination will take place in all phases of the project (months 1 to 48).

Project partners are asked to fill in the information in the Sharepoint table [UPSTREAM WP6 Event tracking](#) each time they submit their relevant event (Figure 30).

Project partner	Event name (in English)	Date	Online or In person	Place of Event	Type of event (media, conference, cleanup, meeting, workshop)	Event link	Role (presenter/moderator/participant)	Number of participant	Type of audience	Short description
NIC	3. International Circular Packaging Conference	20.10.2023	In person	Ljubljana, Slovenia	Conference	3_CPC	Presenter	200-250	Academia, researchers, stakeholders, exhibitors, policymakers	Presentation at the conference: Review of global production and market analysis of bioplastic packaging
UKCEH, WTD	EUROCHARM Stakeholder workshop 2023	11.10.2023	In person	Brussels, Belgium	Workshop, final project meeting	https://www.eurocharm.eu/en/wtd	Stakeholder	~50	Academia, researchers, stakeholders	UKCEH, WTD Stakeholder to the project. Learning status of harmonisation of methods and reporting of filter, plastics and microplastics internationally. Informs T1, UPSTREAM
UKCEH	ETH-Zürich Early Careers Microplastics Workshop, Monte Verità	13 to 17/11/2023	In person	Auzona, Switzerland	Workshop	https://www.workshop2023.ch/	Presenter, moderator	100	Academia, researchers, academia and stakeholders	Early career researchers, academia and stakeholders on methods for monitoring microplastics in waters
EDEN	Launch of BlueMissionHub France	30.11.2023	In person	La Seyne sur Mer, France	Cluster Event	https://edn.edn.eu/EN-5C-TQ	Presenter	~100	Researchers, Stakeholders, Academia, Policymakers	Invited presentation where Eden Tech will be showcasing UPSTREAM and Eden's involvement in the other Mission Ocean projects
UsA	REMEDIÉS Cluster Meeting in Oujda, Morocco	29.11.2023	online	Oujda, Morocco	Cluster Event	https://remediés-for-ocean.eu/news	Presenter	~100	Researchers, Stakeholders, Academia, Policymakers	Invited presentation where Usak will be showcasing UPSTREAM and Usak's involvement in UPSTREAM with the use of CMLO
AITIP	TECHNOLOGICAL BREAKFAST WORKSHOP on "Bioeconomy: introduction to new sustainable solutions and technologies to improve plastic circularity and recycling processes"	23.11.2023	In person	AITIP (Zaragoza, Spain)	Technology workshop	https://www.aitip.es/tema/2023/11/23/	Workshop provider, speaker	~15-20	Professionals, academia	UPSTREAM as example for introducing new sustainable solutions and technologies to improve plastic resource prevention, circularity and recycling processes
UsA	Remove Sorting of Marine Litter Workshop (RSMLW) 2023	16 to 17/10/2023	In person	Nieuweâk, the Netherlands	Workshop	https://2023.eventbrite.com/remote-2023	Presenter	~100	Industry, academia, regulators	Developments of the technology for MP removal, showcasing the UPSTREAM consortium and overall goal of tackling plastic and MP pollution in water
DWS	Microplastics Conference 2024, British Water	8.02.2024	In person	Leeds, UK	conference	https://www.britishwater.co.uk/event	Presenter	~100	Researchers, Stakeholders, Academia, Policymakers	Invited participant for round table where Eden Tech will be showcasing UPSTREAM and Eden's involvement in the other Mission Ocean projects
IDEN	Horizon Europe Mission Day "Regenerating our ocean"	30.01.2024	In person	Paris, France	Cluster Event	https://www.horizon-europe.eu/en/	Participant (Round Table)	~200	Researchers, Stakeholders, Academia, Policymakers	Thinking Out of the Box: Daphnia as a Sentinel Species for Environmental Health and Water Reclamation
DWS/UsB	SEIHC - Europe 14th Annual Meeting	5-9/05/2024	In person	Seville, Spain	conference	https://www.seihc.org/05seville2024	Presenter	~1500	Missions projects, network and EU Missions representatives	Forum to share experiences, build up and foster the dissemination and promotion of Mission Projects
AITIP/NIC	Mission Ocean Communication Working Group	Monthly from Jan.	Online	Online	Workshop Mission Ocean and Waters		Participant	~50	Researchers, Stakeholders, Academia, Industry	Overall framework of UPSTREAM, water pollution and the need of solutions like biodegradable materials in water environments.
AITIP	Biodegradable Materials	13.02.2024	Online	Packnet (Madrid, Spain)	Packnet Working Group	https://packnet.es/evento/03sevilla24	Presenter	~50	Researchers, Stakeholders, Academia, Industry	

Figure 30: UPSTREAM dissemination activities reporting.

Table 1: Dissemination activities (M1-M6).

Type of activities	KPI	M1-M6
Scientific publications	At least 10 publications in total, at least 10 citations per paper 12 months after publication. Targeted publications: Environmental Science and Technology (impact factor: 9.028), Science of the Total Environment (IF: 10.75), and Green Chemistry (IF: 10.18).	1 publication (NIC)
Online media publications	At least 3 results-focused online publications.	-
Attendance at events	Presentations in at least 8 events in total.	Attendance at 11 events
Workshops	10+ workshops held in years 2 - 4 with min. 50 attendees each.	-
Promotion to professional bodies	Presentation to at least 4 events.	-
Linking with other EU and regional initiatives	At least 2 joint events with other projects organised and completed; presence in at least 6 events organised by other projects.	-
Visual ID & brand	At least one update per 10 days. From 100 hits/month in year 1 to 800 hits/month in year 4.	In progress (beta version of website)
Project website	At least one update per 10 days. From 100 hits/month in year 1 to 800 hits/month in year 4.	In progress (beta version of website)
General marketing materials	Comprehensive marketing material pack by M6.	Completed (see Section 3)

Popular science & press articles	At least 3 popular science articles.	-
Social media	At least 1000 (min. 20/month) posts/stories with at least 200000 followers across all channels by M48.	LinkedIn (2632 followers, 15 posts) Facebook (865 followers, 8 posts) X (12 followers, 12 posts) Instagram (61 followers, 10 posts)

To evaluate the dissemination activities' impact, the monitoring will be conducted according to the KPIs listed in the UPSTREAM GA Sections 2.2.2 and 2.2.3. The partners are requested to update the Dissemination Log accordingly, and this will be periodically checked by the WP6 leader.

Communication strategy:

- Social media posts in social networks (LinkedIn, Facebook, X, Instagram).
- Webinars to raise awareness about the project.
- Matchmakings to support innovation activities in demo sites.
- Networking during physical events.
- Newsletters.
- Direct mailing.
- Podcasts.
- Blogs.
- Regular updating of the websites of the project partners.
- Articles (Scientific articles and popular science articles).
- Brochures and flyers.
- Interviews with work package and demo sites leaders.
- Awareness to be raised by the partners during bilateral meetings at regional, national, and European levels (communication activities towards the EU level).

8. Conclusions

In the deliverable D6.1: “Dissemination, Communication, Community Engagement Strategy”, key stakeholder groups, visual identity, social media, webmail, and website were presented in detail.

The promotional materials will create awareness and inform the wide and various target audiences about the UPSTREAM project and its development. These materials will be extensively used by UPSTREAM partners whenever they present at workshops, conferences, publish in journals and magazines, establish contacts with media, attend exhibitions, etc.

The social media and website will raise public awareness of plastic pollution and its environmental impact, encourage participation and support, promote behaviour change and help implement effective solutions to plastic pollution.

All the stakeholders listed in D6.1 are necessary and important for the success of the implementation of the UPSTREAM project. Effective communication can enhance the visibility and recognition of the project and its contributors within relevant fields or communities.

The KPIs have been reached in most cases and all the partners are involved to improve the visibility of the project.

The dissemination plan will be regularly updated during the project. The following steps will be focused on:

- Upgrade the UPSTREAM website
- Design of social media post templates
- Regular activity on social media
- Building UPSTREAM community
- Publish scientific publications
- Attendance at events
- Linking with other EU and regional initiatives